

Regionalised modelling of recycled fertiliser P in agricultural fields: Development of the life cycle inventory model PLCI 2.0

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ABSTRACT

Phosphorus (P) in societal waste streams can be recycled and used as recycled P fertilisers (RPFs). When developing new technologies for P recycling, life cycle assessment (LCA) can be used to assess their environmental impact and support environmentally friendly decisions. In LCA calculations, inventory factors describe, for example, the emissions, resource requirements and potential substitution of products. The Phosphorus Life Cycle Inventory (PLCI) model is a tool for estimating such inventory factors for the use of RPFs.

The main objective of this study was to develop the PLCI model from its previous parameterisation for Denmark to make it applicable to all countries and regions of the EU. This was undertaken by considering parameters that describe regional conditions affecting the loss of P, crop P uptake and potential mineral fertiliser substitution. Such parameters include soil type, soil P status, soil erosion, groundwater leaching, crop types, productivity and crop P concentrations. Several RPFs were incorporated into the model, including coefficients describing the partitioning to the labile, plant-available P fraction.

To illustrate the applicability of the model, a case study was performed. Applications of RPFs were modelled in the Copenhagen region in Denmark and the Piedmont region in Italy. The higher soil erosion rate in Piedmont resulted in over six times greater P loss than in Copenhagen. The difference in P fertilisation practice between the regions had a strong impact on the mineral fertiliser substitutions. The results point to the importance of defining the fertilisation regime of the region being modelled, and this is now possible with the new, more dynamic version of PLCI.

In conclusion, the new PLCI 2.0 model provides a dynamic tool for LCA practitioners to estimate region-specific inventory factors for RPFs. The model is relatively easy to use and captures differences between fertilisers with varying P availability and between applications in different regions of the EU.

1. Introduction

Phosphorus (P) is a finite and non-renewable resource that is essential for crop production. Reinforcing their considerable economic importance and high supply risk, P and phosphate rock are included on the EU's Critical Raw Materials list (EC, 2023). Concurrently, over-fertilisation and excess legacy P in soils in many parts of Europe lead to losses to surface waters and give rise to adverse environmental impacts (Sattari et al., 2012; Sharpley et al., 2013). To protect ecosystems and future food security, the development of circular systems for P and the reduction of losses are crucial. Phosphorus in waste or residual streams

can be recycled and used as recycled P fertilisers (RPFs) (Chojnacka et al., 2020). The life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology has been developed to support environmentally friendly decisions (Bjørn et al., 2018), and is a suitable tool in the development and implementation of new technologies for P recycling (Jensen et al., 2020). For LCA calculations, inventory data are needed to quantify flows, including for example emissions, resource requirements and potential substitution of other products in relation to application of RPFs. A factor that describes the quantity of a flow is hereafter referred to as an inventory factor.

The Phosphorus Life Cycle Inventory Model (PLCI) was developed by ten Hoeve et al. (2018) to provide a tool for LCA practitioners to estimate inventory factors that can be used in the assessment of the

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Abbreviations

(RPF)	Recycled P fertiliser
(PLCI)	Phosphorus Life Cycle Inventory Model
(MPFE)	Mineral P fertiliser equivalency
(Bio-P)	Biosolids, biological P removal
(Chem-P)	Biosolids, chemically precipitated P
(SS ash)	Sewage sludge ash

environmental impact of an RPF after application to an agricultural field. The inventory factors estimated by the model are: 1) the P loss factor, 2) the mineral fertiliser substitution factor and 3) the P harvest factor. The P loss factor describes the loss of P from the field to the surrounding environment in response to the application of an RPF, the mineral fertiliser substitution factor estimates the amount of mineral fertiliser that will not be used by the farmer in response to the application of an RPF, and the P harvest factor describes the potential increase in harvested P after field application of an RPF. [Ten Hoeve et al. \(2018\)](#) demonstrated that these factors can have a substantial influence on the results of an LCA. However, the model was parameterised for Danish conditions only and therefore will have to be reparameterised to be applicable to other regions.

The PLCI model describes the loss of P with a loss factor estimated based on a mass balance over the input and output of P in Danish agriculture. Processes contributing to the loss of P from agricultural land include soil erosion, surface runoff and groundwater leaching, which are all highly dependent on climate, topology, hydrology, soil cover and soil type ([Ge et al., 2023](#)). Moreover, P loss depends on the amount of P in the soil and the crop type. To make the model applicable to other countries or regions, these factors need to be addressed in the model.

The PLCI model also models the substitution of fertiliser (the quantity of conventional mineral fertiliser that the farmer does not apply in response to an application of RPF) in accordance with recommended fertilisation practices in Denmark. However, the potential to substitute mineral fertiliser depends on regulations as well as on recommendations and practices affecting the amount of P that is applied. Such regulatory conditions can have a significant impact on the environmental impacts. This has been shown for example in the LCA study by [Beyers et al. \(2022\)](#) in which differences in regulations had a significant impact on the varying LCA results in different countries. Regulations differ between countries and are sometimes amended ([Amery and Schoumans, 2014](#); [Steinfurth et al., 2022](#)), thus there is a need for a more dynamic model that allows the user to alter the fertilisation regime to fit with the practices relevant for the time and region in which the application takes place.

For calculation of the P harvest factor, there is a need to consider variations between countries in terms of common crop species and how much P is harvested with the respective crops. The amount of harvested P varies significantly between countries and regions depending on crop type, productivity and crop P concentration ([Panagos et al., 2022b](#)). In the PLCI model developed by [ten Hoeve et al. \(2018\)](#), the maximum crop P uptake is described as a constant, parameterised on the basis of the most common crops in Denmark, assuming that the corresponding maximum P uptake of each crop is equal to the amount of P that is recommended for fertilisation in Denmark. To capture the differences in harvested P between countries, a new approach is needed for estimation of crop P uptake.

The current recommendation of the World Food LCA Database is to use the SALCA-P model for estimation of P loss ([Nemecek et al., 2019](#)). The SALCA model was developed considering the soil and climate conditions of Switzerland ([Oberholzer et al., 2012](#)) and requires input data on mean soil erosion rate, slope shape, length and steepness of the agricultural field for example ([Prasuhn, 2006](#)). Such variables are

generally difficult to estimate, especially on a regional average level. In addition, SALCA-P does not estimate the substitution of mineral P fertiliser as a consequence of the application of RPF products.

There are several other models that model P dynamics on different scales ([van der Salm et al., 2016](#); [Wang et al., 2020](#)). These models generally have a high level of complexity, making them difficult to use for an LCA practitioner who is not an expert in P modelling. Moreover, the aim of an LCA involving land application of an RPF is often to model the general impact of application of the RPF in any field within a given country or region, rather than in one specific field. High-precision models often require input data on specific soil properties, rendering these models less suitable for estimation of inventory factors for LCA. This was the rationale for developing an alternative, simpler approach such as the PLCI model. Furthermore, the PLCI model is unique in that it calculates inventory factors suitable for an LCA on RPFs in a broader systems perspective.

The main objective of the present study was to develop the PLCI model further to be applicable to regions of the European Union's member states, by considering parameters that describe regional conditions affecting the loss of P, crop P uptake and potential mineral fertiliser substitution, and verifying that the model results in sensible relationships between the input parameters and the inventory factors. Target users of the model are LCA practitioners who wish to perform an LCA on a P recycling technology, applied to agricultural fields in any region in the EU. The aim was therefore to provide a model that would not require detailed site-specific data and where the user would not need expertise in P modelling. Furthermore, the objective was to illustrate the applicability of the model by conducting a case study in which the inventory factors for various RPFs applied in different regions were calculated. It was hypothesised that the region in which an RPF is applied has a greater impact on the inventory factors than the type of RPF when comparing widely diverging European regions and widely differing RPF types. The hypothesis was based on the results of [ten Hoeve et al. \(2018\)](#), who saw greater differences between different farm types (arable and pig farms) than between different fertilisers.

2. Method

2.1. Model description

2.1.1. P pools

The structure of the PLCI model published in [ten Hoeve et al. \(2018\)](#) was developed further in this study to include more of the interactions between different forms of P so that it now includes five P pools. An overview of the modelling framework is given in [Fig. 1](#). The pools include plant-available labile P (P_L), a residual, more slowly available fertiliser P pool (P_{res}), P bound (mainly by adsorption) to secondary minerals (P_{sec}), inorganic apatite-like P precipitates (P_{apa}), and plant-unavailable inorganic and organic P (P_{na}).

Initialisation of the P pools was undertaken using data on Olsen-P ([Ballabio et al., 2016](#)) and total P ([Panagos et al., 2022a](#)) from the Land Use and Cover Area frame Statistical survey (LUCAS). Olsen-P data (mg kg^{-1}) were used as an estimate of the plant-available labile P (P_L), converted to kg P ha^{-1} by multiplication with the regional average soil bulk density (g cm^{-3}). The soil bulk density was derived from soil texture maps by [Ballabio et al. \(2016\)](#), using soil texture data from the LUCAS survey. The depth of the topsoil modelled was 20 cm, similar to the topsoil sampling in LUCAS.

Inorganic P bound to secondary minerals (P_{sec}) was estimated using the Langmuir equation, assuming that P_{sec} is in equilibrium with P_L ([Ringeval et al., 2017](#)). P_{apa} was initialised as 20 % of total P, based on the model output of [Ringeval et al. \(2017\)](#), and the remaining P total was partitioned to the unavailable pool (P_{na}) after deduction of P_L and P_{sec} .

When a P fertiliser is added, the total fertiliser P (inorganic and organic P) partitions between the labile plant-available pool P_L and the residual pool P_{res} . ρ is the amount of fertiliser added (kg P ha^{-1}), and f is

Fig. 1. Model framework overview (adapted from ten Hoeve et al. (2018) and Ringeval et al. (2017)). The soil pools include plant-available labile P (P_L), a residual, more slowly available fertiliser P pool (P_{res}), P bound to secondary minerals (P_{sec}), apatite P (P_{apo}), and unavailable P (P_{na}). P fertiliser application ρ (kg ha^{-1}) partitions between P_L and P_{res} , is described by the partitioning coefficient f . Residual release of P from P_{res} is described by the slow release factor μ_{res} . Other inputs of P include atmospheric deposition δ to P_{apo} and P_L , and weathering ω . P gradually becomes plant unavailable, as described by the occlusion constant γ .

the RPF-specific partitioning factor, describing the share of P that is partitioned to P_L . Phosphorus is slowly released from P_{res} to P_L as described by the release constant μ_{res} , which was calibrated by ten Hoeve et al. (2018) (then called the mobilisation factor). The P in the labile pool that is taken up by plants is removed from the soil as harvested P ($P_{harvest}$). A fraction of the labile P is dissolved in the soil solution and is prone to leaching ($P_{leaching}$). The P loss with soil erosion $P_{erosion}$ is modelled as proportional to the total P in the soil.

Atmospheric deposition of P, δ ($\text{kg P ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), was modelled by Ringeval et al. (2017) on a global scale using data from Wang et al. (2014). Regional averages were calculated in the present study. The P deposition was modelled with equal distribution between P_{apo} and P_L , adopting a simplified approach to that of Ringeval et al. (2017) (detailed description in the Appendix section A.1.1).

The release rate of phosphate-P by weathering of minerals, ω ($\text{kg P ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$), was calibrated by Wang et al. (2010) for each soil order (Table A.1 in the Appendix). The rate at which secondary P becomes unavailable was assumed to be proportional to the size of the P_{sec} pool, with the occlusion constant $\gamma = 1.2 \cdot e^{-5}$ (year^{-1}) (Ringeval et al., 2017), as pre-calibrated by Yang et al. (2014):

$$P_{sec \rightarrow occ} = P_{sec} \cdot \gamma \quad (1)$$

The model runs with 10 timesteps per year, since ten Hoeve et al. (2018) verified that this was low enough to avoid significant numerical errors. The modelling period was 500 years. As the timeframe considered in an LCA varies between LCA methodologies and the wishes of the LCA modeller, the inventory factors were calculated throughout the modelling period. The model considers regions down to the NUTS3 level, to the extent of EU countries. NUTS stands for Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics and NUTS regions are commonly used for statistics in Europe (Eurostat, 2022).

2.1.2. Fertiliser application

To estimate the consequences of RPF land application, a single application in the first year was simulated. The impact of the RPF application was estimated in relation to a reference simulation without

fertiliser application in the first year. In the following years in both simulations, mineral P fertiliser was applied according to the regulations or fertilisation recommendations of the region. The RPF-specific partitioning factor, f , was estimated from the mineral P fertiliser equivalency (MPFE) values determined for the RPFs considered in the publication of Möller et al. (2018). MPFE is an estimate of the P-uptake efficiency (harvested P in a treated-unfertilised control) of an RPF treatment vs. P-uptake efficiency of a reference water-soluble fertiliser (e.g. triple super phosphate). Assuming that all the P in mineral fertiliser is labile, the MPFE values provide an estimate of the share of P in RPFs that is partitioned to the labile pool.

2.1.3. Langmuir equation

The exchange between labile P and P bound in secondary minerals was assumed to be in equilibrium. The Langmuir equation was used (Ringeval et al., 2017):

$$P_{sec} = \frac{S_{max} \cdot P_L}{K_s + P_L} \quad (2)$$

The parameters S_{max} and K_s (both kg P ha^{-1}) were calibrated for each soil order by Wang et al. (2010), based on Gross and Schlesinger (1995). S_{max} is the maximum P sorption capacity of the soil and K_s is the half saturation constant. The most common soil order in each NUTS region was estimated based on the FAO-UNESCO (2023) Soil Map of the World using the USDA soil taxonomy (Soil Survey Staff, 1999).

2.1.4. Calculation of P harvest

Similar to the previous version of the model, the harvested crop P was calculated using Michaelis-Menten kinetics:

$$P_{harvest} = \frac{\alpha_{max} \cdot P_L}{K_m + P_L} \quad (3)$$

where α_{max} is the maximum yearly crop P uptake ($\text{kg P ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$) and K_m is the half-saturation constant (kg P ha^{-1}). Ten Hoeve et al. (2018) calculated K_m and α_{max} based on data on crop P uptake in Denmark, using data from a long-term soil P depletion trial (van der Bom et al., 2017) for calculation of K_m . The relation between K_m and α_{max} from ten Hoeve et al. (2018) was used in PLCI 2.0 to estimate K_m , assuming this relation to be constant: $K_m = 1.578 \cdot \alpha_{max}$.

α_{max} was calculated for each country based on the most common crops of the country, as the P demand of each crop weighted by the areal coverage of the crop. Only crops with an area coverage $>1\%$ were included in the calculations:

$$\alpha_{max} = \frac{\sum (P \text{ demand} \cdot \text{Areal coverage})}{\text{Total area}} \quad (4)$$

The P demand ($\text{kg P ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$) of each crop was estimated as the total P removal with the main product and harvested residues:

$$P \text{ demand} = P \text{ removal}_{\text{main prod}} + P \text{ removal}_{\text{res}} \quad (5)$$

The total area (ha) is the sum of the areal coverage of all crops in each country. Data on areal coverage were taken from FAOSTAT (2020).

The P removal with the main product of each crop was then calculated:

$$P \text{ removal}_{\text{main prod}} = P \text{ content}_{\text{main prod}} \cdot \text{Yield} \quad (6)$$

For the P content of each crop $P \text{ content}_{\text{main prod}}$ (kg P kg^{-1} fresh matter), data from Helin and Weikard (2019) were used. The average crop yields of common crops in the EU were estimated based on ten years' (2011–2020) statistics from FAOSTAT (2020).

To calculate the P removal with residues, the amount of residues removed was multiplied by the P content of residues, which was set to 0.11 % per dry matter, similar to the assumption made by Panagos et al. (2022b). The P removal with residues was calculated:

$$P \text{ removal}_{\text{res}} = R_{\text{res,prod}} \cdot \text{Yield} \cdot DM_{\text{frac}} \cdot R_{\text{res,removed}} \cdot P \text{ content}_{\text{res}} \quad (7)$$

where $R_{res, prod}$ is the ratio of residues produced per Mg of crop produced and $R_{res, removed}$ is the ratio of residues removed from the field. DM_{frac} is the dry matter fraction of the crop (kg kg^{-1}). Data on $R_{res, prod}$, $R_{res, removed}$ and DM_{frac} from Panagos et al. (2022b) were used. Data on the parameters for calculation of P removal with residues for some example crops are included in Table A.2.

For perennial trees such as fruit and nut trees, the following equation was used to estimate the amount of P removed with residues:

$$P_{removal, res, trees} = \left(\frac{P_{removal, fruit}}{R_{P \text{ to fruit}}} - P_{removal, fruit} \right) \bullet P_{content, res} \quad (8)$$

It was assumed that the P taken up by the tree is permanently removed from the soil, as some is removed with pruning and some is stored in the tree trunk until the tree is eventually cut down and removed from the field. The ratio of P uptake partitioned to the fruit and foliage was assumed to be 21.3 %, based on an experiment in which the P uptake of apple trees and the partitioning of P was measured for 11 months (Yan et al., 2007). Differences in the partitioning between tree species were not included due to the lack of available data.

2.1.5. Calculation of P leaching

Leaching of P (kg P ha^{-1}) was estimated using equation (9):

$$P_{leaching} = GWR \bullet P_{CaCl2} \bullet R \quad (9)$$

where GWR is the regional average annual groundwater recharge (m year^{-1}), which is an estimate of the amount of water percolating through the soil and reaching the groundwater. P_{CaCl2} is the CaCl_2 -extractable P (mg L^{-1}) (Houba et al., 2000), which is a representation of the P dissolved in the soil solution in the topsoil, and R is a retention factor that was calibrated to reflect the share of P_{CaCl2} that goes into the groundwater. Annual average GWR was derived for each NUTS region from modelled data from de Graaf et al. (2019), who simulated dynamic global groundwater-surface water interactions in three 30-year (2010–2039) simulations with different climate models (details in Appendix section A.1.2).

P_{CaCl2} was estimated as a fraction of P_L , based on data from Wuenschel et al. (2015) on Olsen-P and CaCl_2 -P of 50 central European soils:

$$P_{CaCl2} (\text{mg L}^{-1}) = 0.0375 \bullet P_L (\text{mg kg}^{-1}) \bullet 0.10 (\text{kg L}^{-1}) \quad (10)$$

Measurements of Olsen-P and CaCl_2 -P from three articles (Braun et al., 2019; Dodd et al., 2012; Neri et al., 2005), in total data from 31 soil samples, were used for validation of equation (10). P_{CaCl2} was calculated from the measured Olsen-P of the samples using equation (10). The correlation between the predicted P_{CaCl2} and the measured CaCl_2 -P was calculated, giving a Pearson's correlation coefficient of $r = 0.58$, as with the correlation between CaCl_2 -P and Olsen-P, which was also estimated by Blombäck et al. (2021) to be $r = 0.59$. As the relation between CaCl_2 -P and Olsen-P depends on soil properties, the calculation of P_{CaCl2} from P_L introduces uncertainty.

The retention factor R was calibrated based on measured concentrations of total P in groundwater at groundwater stations in Europe. The stations included were 70 stations in Germany (81 samples), one in Belgium (nine samples) and three in Croatia (16 samples) (GEMStat, 2015). Samples from 2015 were used as this was the sampling year closest in time to the soil P status data used in this model. The median groundwater P concentration of each country was obtained from the GEMStat database. The retention factor R was calibrated to match the calculated average P_{CaCl2} of the four countries with the measured median P in groundwater in the country. In the calibration, a weight was assigned to each country based on the number of stations. Finally, the retention factor was obtained: $R = 0.95 \text{ kg mg}^{-1} \text{ L m}^{-1} \text{ ha}^{-1}$.

2.1.6. Calculation of P loss with soil erosion

The loss of P with soil erosion was calculated as the soil loss multi-

plied by the total P in the soil:

$$P_{erosion} = P_{tot} \bullet SE_a \quad (11)$$

SE_a ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is the area-weighted regional average soil erosion from arable land, for which data modelled by Panagos et al. (2015) were used (described in the Appendix section A.1.4).

For validation of equation (11), a comparison with measured P loss was made. Kronvang et al. (2007) measured the loss of total P from agriculture-intensive areas between 1993 and 2002 at the outlet of six micro-catchments in Denmark and Sweden. The mean annual measured P loss of the micro-catchments was compared with calculated $P_{erosion}$ for the corresponding NUTS3 regions in which the micro-catchments are located. The calculated $P_{erosion}$ was on average 2.9 times higher than the losses measured by Kronvang et al. (2007). A higher calculated value had been anticipated, since the PLCI 2.0 only calculates losses from the field and does not include the successive fate of the P. Deposition is expected on the way from a field to the catchment outlet, where the measurements were taken. The calculated and measured concentrations correlate by Pearson's correlation coefficient $r = 0.65$ (Table A.3).

2.1.7. Calculation of inventory factors

The inventory factor for P loss ($F_{P_{Loss}}$) was calculated according to equation (12). $F_{P_{Loss}}$ describes the increased loss of P in the model run with the initial application of RPF in the first year compared with the reference model run without fertiliser application in the first year, per kg applied recycled P:

$$F_{P_{Loss}} = \frac{P_{Loss, Wi} - P_{Loss, Ref}}{\rho_{RPF}} \quad (12)$$

where P_{Loss} is the total loss of P, calculated as the sum of the P lost with erosion and leaching:

$$P_{loss} = P_{erosion} + P_{leaching} \quad (13)$$

where $P_{Loss, Wi}$ is the loss of P in the model run with the initial application of an RPF (denoted Wi) and $P_{Loss, Ref}$ is the loss of P in the reference model run (denoted Ref). Finally, ρ_{RPF} is the application of RPF (kg ha^{-1}) in the first year.

Similarly, the inventory factor for harvested P ($F_{P_{Harvest}}$) is calculated according to equation (14), and the mineral P fertiliser substitution factor ($F_{P_{PFS}}$) is calculated according to equation (15):

$$F_{P_{Harvest}} = \frac{P_{Uptake, Wi} - P_{Uptake, Ref}}{\rho_{RPF}} \quad (14)$$

$$F_{P_{PFS}} = \frac{\Sigma \rho_{MF, Ref} - \Sigma \rho_{MF, Wi}}{\rho_{RPF}} \quad (15)$$

where $\Sigma \rho_{MF, Ref}$ and $\Sigma \rho_{MF, Wi}$ are the sum of mineral fertiliser applied throughout the reference model run and the model run with the initial application of RPF respectively. The inventory factors of an RPF can also be calculated relative to a mineral fertilizer, as described in ten Hoeve et al. (2018).

2.2. Case study

To investigate how regional conditions and fertiliser regulations affect the inventory factors, a case study was performed. RPFs were applied in two different regions: the Copenhagen region in Denmark (NUTS3 region code DK012, areal extent 342 km^2) and the Piedmont region in Italy (NUTS2 region code ITC1, areal extent $25,402 \text{ km}^2$). A Danish region was chosen for comparability with the previous version of the PLCI model (ten Hoeve et al., 2018) and a region in Italy was chosen due to the high soil erosion in the country, which was hypothesised to have an effect on $F_{P_{Loss}}$ in particular. The rules and recommendations for fertiliser application also differ between the two countries, which was hypothesised would affect the $F_{P_{PFS}}$ in particular. The Piedmont region

was chosen due to its great importance to agricultural production in Italy. A NUTS2 region was selected due to the availability of statistics on the crop distribution and fertiliser guidelines at NUTS2-region level, and not at NUTS3 level. The regional average values of soil parameters in the two regions are presented in Table 1.

In the first year of the simulations in both regions, 90 kg P ha⁻¹ was applied with an RPF. The RPFs were struvite (magnesium ammonium phosphate, which can be recovered from wastewater (Wu and Vaneckhaute, 2022)), biologically or chemically precipitated biosolids (Bio-P and Chem-P) or untreated sewage-sludge ash (SS ash), with the partitioning coefficients f presented in Table 2. An amount of 90 kg P ha⁻¹ is the maximum permitted P application with waste products every three years in Denmark (Danish Ministry of the Environment, 2006). In the following years, the application of mineral P fertiliser was modelled to follow regional or national fertiliser regulations or recommendations of Copenhagen and Piedmont, respectively (Figs. A.1–A.5), hereafter referred to as fertilisation strategies.

The fertilisation strategy in Denmark was the same as that modelled by ten Hoeve et al. (2018) for an arable farm. The amount of mineral P fertiliser applied was determined based on Olsen-P measurements, such that when Olsen-P was 20 mg kg⁻¹ or lower, the amount applied was 1.5 times the maximum crop P uptake α_{max} . For Olsen-P levels between 20 and 60 mg kg⁻¹, the multiplication factor was described by a linear function, and for Olsen-P > 60 mg kg⁻¹, the amount applied was 0.2 times the maximum crop P uptake α_{max} (ten Hoeve et al., 2018) (Figs. A.1 and A.2).

In Piedmont, the fertilisation strategy was assumed to follow the voluntary regional guidelines (Disciplinari di Produzione Integrata, 2022). The recommendations are that when Olsen-P is above 25 mg kg⁻¹, no mineral P fertiliser should be applied, and when Olsen-P is below 25 mg kg⁻¹, P can be applied to meet the crop demand. Again, the crop demand was assumed to be equal to α_{max} .

In the Copenhagen region, α_{max} was estimated based on the crop distribution in Denmark. In Piedmont, the crop distribution differs substantially from the average crop distribution in Italy. Therefore, α_{max} was estimated based on the most common crops in the Piedmont region, which are maize (40 %), rice (31 %), wheat (18 %) and grape (11 %), when excluding pastures, rotational meadows and permanent grassland (CREA, 2021).

To test the hypothesis that the region has a greater impact on inventory factors than the type of RPF, the percentage difference between the regions was calculated for each RPF, as well as the percentage difference between the RPFs with the highest and lowest inventory factors in Copenhagen and Piedmont.

2.3. Sensitivity analysis

To analyse the sensitivity of the inventory factors to different parameters, the Copenhagen region was selected for a sensitivity analysis by changing one parameter at a time. The average values of the Copenhagen region and the high and low values tested are listed in Table A.4. The high and low values were selected to represent realistic values that occur in some regions in the EU. The partitioning factor f was set to 0.5 in the sensitivity tests of other parameters. For Olsen-P, total P, α_{max} and application of RPF in year 1 (ρ_{RPF}), the Copenhagen standard value was changed to 50 % higher and 50 % lower values. For SE_a , GWR

Table 1

Regional average values of soil parameters in the Copenhagen region (DK012) and Piedmont region (ITC1). The maximum crop P uptake (α_{max}) (kg P ha⁻¹) in Piedmont was estimated based on the most common crops in the region, while α_{max} in Copenhagen is the country average. ω is the weathering rate (kg P ha⁻¹), S_{max} is the maximum P sorption capacity of the soil (kg P ha⁻¹), K_s is the half saturation constant (kg P ha⁻¹), GWR is the groundwater recharge (m), SE_a is the soil erosion from arable land (Mg ha⁻¹), and δ is the atmospheric deposition (kg P ha⁻¹).

Region	Olsen-P	Total P	α_{max}	ω	Soil type	S_{max}	$1/K_s$	GWR	SE_a	δ
Copenhagen	30	734	24	0.5	Inceptisols	770	650	0.26	0.6	0.11
Piedmont	28	810	20	0.5	Inceptisols	770	650	0.22	3.5	0.10

Table 2

Partitioning coefficients (f) of RPFs modelled in the case study.

RPF	Abbreviation	f
Struvite		1.0
Biosolid, biologic precipitate	Bio-P	0.90
Biosolid, chemical precipitate	Chem-P	0.54
Sewage-sludge ash	SS ash	0.34

and δ , the high and the low values were selected based on the highest and lowest occurring country average among the EU countries.

For the constants of the model, including the occlusion constant γ , leaching retention factor R and residual P release μ_{res} , the sensitivity was tested by changing the value to 50 % higher and 50 % lower than the default. The sensitivity to the soil order was also tested by changing the soil order, thus changing K_s , S_{max} and weathering ω at the same time.

3. Results

3.1. Case study

In Piedmont, $F_{P_{Loss}}$ is between six and seven times higher than in the Copenhagen region, mostly due to the higher soil erosion rate (Fig. 2), which is 5.8 times greater in this region. The relative difference in $F_{P_{Loss}}$ between the fertilisers is similar in Denmark and in Italy. In both regions, more P is lost when the direct plant-available P fraction of the fertiliser is lower, because a larger proportion remains in the soil, rather than being taken up by plants, and is lost over time with soil erosion.

For $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ the trend in Copenhagen is that an RPF with higher partitioning to P_L has a higher $F_{P_{Harvest}}$. For SS ash, Chem-P and Bio-P, $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ increases over time due to the slow release of residual P. For struvite, $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ is essentially stable after 25 years as there is no residual P at that time. After 300 years, the $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ of Bio-P is similar to that of struvite.

In Piedmont, the $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ of struvite is the highest of the fertilisers at the start of the simulation, but quickly reaches a final steady value as all the struvite P is either harvested soon after application or is lost. Over a 100-year period and longer, struvite has the lowest $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ compared with the fertilisers that continue to release P slowly throughout the modelling period. The slow release leads to the fact that there is never more P released than the crops can take up. Even though the P loss rate in Piedmont is relatively high compared with other regions in Europe (Panagos et al., 2015), it is still much lower than the crop P uptake.

In the Copenhagen region, $F_{P_{FFS}}$ follows the same trend as $F_{P_{Harvest}}$. Struvite has an $F_{P_{FFS}}$ of 0.66 after five years, and after year 20 it is 0.87. This means that in a simulation where struvite is added, 87 % of the P added is replacing mineral P application in the following years. Since the application modelled was 90 kg P ha⁻¹, the mineral P requirements in the following years are reduced by 78 kg P ha⁻¹.

In Piedmont, the $F_{P_{FFS}}$ of struvite and Bio-P are the same for the first seven years because the application of these RPFs results in no mineral fertiliser being applied in the following seven years due to the higher Olsen-P level and the applied fertilisation strategy (Fig. A.5). When Olsen-P has decreased to values below 20 mg kg⁻¹, mineral P is applied again to meet the crop demand. Olsen-P then increases once more, so there is no P application in the following year. The alternation between

Fig. 2. The P loss factor F_{PLoss} (a and b), P harvest factor $F_{PHarvest}$ (c and d) and P fertiliser substitution factor F_{PFS} (e and f) of RPFs applied in Copenhagen and Piedmont. The RPFs are struvite, biosolid from treatment with biological P removal (Bio-P), chemically precipitated biosolid (Chem-P) and sewage-sludge ash (SS ash).

application and no application from year to year gives an oscillating curve for F_{PFS} . The F_{PFS} of SS ash has a pattern similar to that of struvite and Bio-P, but the substitution is lower due to the lower partitioning (f) to P_L .

When mineral fertiliser application starts again after RPF application, the amount applied is the same as in the reference model run in Piedmont. In Copenhagen, however, mineral fertiliser is applied already the year after RPF application, and F_{PFS} gradually increases due to the linear function for P application depending on Olsen-P (Figs. A.2–A.4).

In Piedmont, mineral fertiliser application starts again five years after application of Chem-P. The Chem-P has the same substitution factor throughout the modelling period after year 5, while the other fertilisers alternate between two values. The stability of the F_{PFS} of Chem-P is due to the equal application timing as in the reference model run without P application in the first year (Fig. A.5), meaning that mineral fertiliser is applied in the same year in the reference model run

as in the model run with Chem-P application.

The percentage difference between the regions for each RPF was highest for F_{PLoss} , lowest for F_{PFS} and intermediate for $F_{PHarvest}$ (Table 3a). The difference between the regions was greater for RPFs with lower partitioning to P_L such as SS ash. Within a region, the difference between the RPFs was also highest for F_{PLoss} and lowest for F_{PFS} , and the difference was greater in Piedmont than in Copenhagen (Table 3b). Comparing the percentage difference between RPFs and between the regions, it is difficult to establish whether the region or type of RPF affects the results most. This invalidates the hypothesis that the regions affect the inventory factors more than fertiliser type.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis

The results of the sensitivity analysis on the Copenhagen regional average Olsen-P, total P, α_{max} and the amount of fertiliser applied in the

Table 3

a) Average percentage difference in the inventory factors between the regions for each RPF, b) average percentage difference between the RPFs with the highest and the lowest inventory factors within a region. For both a) and b), the average was calculated by establishing the percentage difference for each timestep of the model, and then calculating the average for each RPF or region. Included are the P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, the P harvest factor $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and the P fertiliser substitution factor $F_{P_{FS}}$ of RPFs applied in Copenhagen and Piedmont. The RPFs are struvite, biologically precipitated biosolid (Bio-P), chemically precipitated biosolid (Chem-P) and sewage-sludge ash (SS ash).

a) RPF	$F_{P_{Loss}}$	$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	$F_{P_{FS}}$
Struvite	133 %	31 %	9 %
Bio-P	138 %	50 %	15 %
Chem-P	147 %	102 %	52 %
SS-ash	149 %	118 %	82 %
Average	142 %	75 %	39 %
b) Region			
Copenhagen	103 %	22 %	11 %
Piedmont	123 %	87 %	94 %

first year (ρ) are presented in Table 4. Graphs showing how the inventory factors vary with time can be found in Figures A.7–A.17.

3.2.1. Regional parameters

Olsen-P, which is used to initialise the P_L pool, has a high impact on $F_{P_{Harvest}}$. When Olsen-P is low, P is limiting plant growth, so an application of RPF results in a large proportion of the RPF-P being taken up by the plants and harvested in the years following RPF application. When Olsen-P is high, plants already have enough P. Therefore the difference in P harvest is lower between the reference model run and the model run with application of RPF. $F_{P_{FS}}$ is positively correlated with Olsen-P. With a higher Olsen-P, the application of RPF results in very little mineral P application being needed for a long time in subsequent years. With low Olsen-P, the labile P is taken up by plants directly, so more mineral P fertiliser is needed again the next year.

The maximum crop P uptake (α_{max}) has a relatively high impact on $F_{P_{Loss}}$ and $F_{P_{Harvest}}$. A higher α_{max} leads to higher plant uptake of the RPF-P and a higher $F_{P_{Harvest}}$. Thus, less P remains in the soil and can be lost by leaching and erosion, giving a lower $F_{P_{Loss}}$. As plants take up more of the labile P when α_{max} is higher, less P is left in labile pool the following year, meaning that higher mineral P application is needed and the $F_{P_{FS}}$ will be lower. Varying total P showed a very low impact on the inventory factors. The impact of atmospheric deposition (δ) was also very low (Table 5).

The sensitivity test on SE_a confirmed that a high soil erosion rate

Table 4

The 100 year-inventory factors (P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, P harvest factor, $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and mineral P fertiliser substitution factor, $F_{P_{FS}}$) obtained from modelling with the regional average Olsen-P, total P, maximum crop P uptake (α_{max}) and 90 kg P applied in the first year (ρ_{RPF}), and when each of these parameters is changed to a 50 % lower or 50 % higher value. The percentual change in the inventory factor when a parameter is changed up or down is presented in the right-hand columns.

	50 % lower	Standard value	50 % higher	%Change with lower value	%Change with higher value
$F_{P_{Loss}}$					
Olsen-P	0.0095	0.0093	0.0094	2.0%	0.7%
Total P	0.0093	0.0093	0.0094	-0.3%	0.1%
α_{max}	0.0093	0.0093	0.0087	0.0%	-6.7%
ρ_{RPF}	0.0095	0.0093	0.0093	2.0%	-0.6%
$F_{P_{Harvest}}$					
Olsen-P	0.17	0.10	0.08	58.5%	-20.4%
Total P	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.0%	0.0%
α_{max}	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.0%	10.9%
ρ_{RPF}	0.11	0.10	0.10	7.2%	-5.9%
$F_{P_{FS}}$					
Olsen-P	0.60	0.66	0.68	-9.3%	3.2%
Total P	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.0%	0.0%
α_{max}	0.66	0.66	0.65	0.0%	-1.4%
ρ_{RPF}	0.65	0.66	0.66	-1.1%	0.9%

leads to greater losses of the RPF-P applied. Changing SE_a from the regional average of Copenhagen (0.6 kg soil $ha^{-1} year^{-1}$) to the average in Italy (8.4 kg soil $ha^{-1} year^{-1}$), the 100-year $F_{P_{Loss}}$ increased by a factor of 12. The impact on $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and $F_{P_{FS}}$ was lower, but a clear negative effect was found that increases over time (Figs. A.14 and A.15). With greater soil erosion, more of the RPF-P is lost before it can be taken up by plants and harvested, leading to lower $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and $F_{P_{FS}}$.

The sensitivity test on GWR showed almost no impact on $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ or $F_{P_{FS}}$ (Table 5). However, the impact on $F_{P_{Loss}}$ was high. To test whether the impact of GWR was less significant in an area with greater soil erosion, a similar sensitivity test was performed for the Piedmont region. In Copenhagen, the 100-year $F_{P_{Loss}}$ increased by 26 % when changing GWR from the lowest to the highest value. In Piedmont, the increase was 6 % (Figs. A.16 and A.17). This confirms the greater sensitivity of GWR in regions where soil erosion is low, as leaching is responsible for a larger share of P loss.

3.2.2. Soil order

The 100-year inventory factors of the Copenhagen region, obtained from modelling with different soil orders, are presented in Table 6. The soil order affects $F_{P_{Loss}}$ the most, showing a 27 % difference between the highest and the lowest value. $F_{P_{Loss}}$ correlates positively ($r = 0.8$) with the maximum sorption capacity (S_{max}). High S_{max} increases the sorption of labile P to secondary minerals. Thus, less P is taken up by plants and a greater fraction is lost over time with soil erosion.

3.2.3. Fertiliser application

The amount of RPF applied in the first year (ρ_{RPF}) has a relatively low impact on the inventory factors, since they are expressed per kg of fertiliser P applied (Table 4). The factor most affected is $F_{P_{Harvest}}$, which is affected negatively. A high P application may exceed the plant demand. The RPF-P not needed for the plants can be lost or adsorbed to the P_{sec} pool, and further to P_{na} .

The partitioning coefficient f correlates negatively with $F_{P_{Loss}}$ (Table 7 and Figs. A.18–A.20). The smaller the labile fraction of the RPF, the more will be lost with soil erosion before becoming plant-available, as also seen in the case study. $F_{P_{Loss}}$ decreases by 80 % in a sensitivity test where f is changed from 0 to 1, indicating a high sensitivity. The longer the timeframe considered, the greater the impact of f , as more is lost over time when f is low.

$F_{P_{Harvest}}$ correlates positively with f . The greater the labile fraction, the higher the $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ in the first years. After 500 years, the difference between the fertilisers becomes smaller due to the slow release of residual P from the RPFs with low f . Similarly, there is a positive effect on $F_{P_{FS}}$, meaning that an RPF with more labile P (higher f) can substitute

Table 5

The 100 year-inventory factors (P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, P harvest factor, $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and mineral P fertiliser substitution factor $F_{P_{FS}}$) obtained from modelling with the regional average soil erosion rate SE_a , groundwater recharge GWR , and atmospheric deposition δ , and when each of these parameters is changed to a lower or higher value. The standard value is the regional average of the Copenhagen region, and the high and the low values were selected to represent realistic values that occur in some regions in the EU. The percentual change in the inventory factor when a parameter is changed from the low to the high value is presented in the right-hand column.

Tested parameter		Low value	Standard	High value	Unit	%Change from lowest to highest
SE_a	value	0.46	0.61	8.4	kg soil ha ⁻¹	
	$F_{P_{Loss}}$	0.01	0.01	0.11	kg kg ⁻¹	1379 %
	$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	0.10	0.10	0.10	kg kg ⁻¹	-2.9 %
	$F_{P_{FS}}$	0.66	0.66	0.63	kg kg ⁻¹	-4.8 %
GWR	value	0.06	0.26	0.71	m	
	$F_{P_{Loss}}$	0.01	0.01	0.01	kg kg ⁻¹	26 %
	$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	0.10	0.10	0.10	kg kg ⁻¹	0.0 %
	$F_{P_{FS}}$	0.66	0.66	0.66	kg kg ⁻¹	-0.3 %
δ	value	0.02	0.11	0.28	kg P ha ⁻¹	
	$F_{P_{Loss}}$	0.01	0.01	0.01	kg kg ⁻¹	0.0 %
	$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	0.11	0.10	0.10	kg kg ⁻¹	-0.3 %
	$F_{P_{FS}}$	0.66	0.66	0.66	kg kg ⁻¹	0.0 %

more mineral P fertiliser, especially in the first years after application. After 500 years, the substitution of the different RPFs evens out to be almost the same, but in an area where soil erosion is higher, the difference would probably be greater.

3.2.4. Sensitivity to the constants of the model

The sensitivity analysis of the model constants (Table 8) indicates that the slow-release factor (μ_{Res}) has a greater impact on the inventory factors of SS ash than Bio-P, due to the larger fraction of residual P in SS ash. The mobilisation constant calibrated by ten Hoeve et al. (2018) was used as a common μ_{res} for all RPF fertilisers in the present study. In reality, the rate at which P becomes plant-available varies between RPFs (Glæsner et al., 2019). The sensitivity analysis shows that calibration of μ_{res} would improve the precision of the model, especially for RPFs with low direct plant P availability, while the importance of μ_{res} is lower for RPFs with high f . However, the rate at which P becomes available is largely dependent on the soil characteristics. Therefore, further calibration of μ_{res} would require data on the long-term P availability of different RPFs applied to contrasting soil types. Such datasets were not found.

A higher μ_{res} affects $F_{P_{Loss}}$ negatively because a faster release leads to more P becoming plant-available and harvested instead of lost with soil erosion. For the same reason, both $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and $F_{P_{FS}}$ correlate positively with μ_{res} . With a higher μ_{res} , more of the RPF-P becomes plant-available sooner, meaning that less mineral fertiliser is needed and leading to a faster increase in $F_{P_{FS}}$.

$F_{P_{Loss}}$ correlates positively with the occlusion constant (γ). A higher occlusion rate means that more of the RPF-P becomes unavailable before being taken up by plants. Consequently, a larger share is lost by soil

Table 6

Inventory factors (P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, P harvest factor $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and mineral P fertiliser substitution factor $F_{P_{FS}}$) for a 100-year modelling period of the Copenhagen region, with changing soil order.

Soil order	$F_{P_{Loss}}$	$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	$F_{P_{FS}}$
Alfisol/Spodosol	0.010	0.106	0.656
Andisol/Aridisol	0.009	0.106	0.656
Entisol	0.009	0.105	0.657
Gelisol/Histosol/Inceptisol	0.009	0.105	0.657
Mollisol	0.009	0.106	0.656
Oxisol	0.012	0.106	0.656
Ultisol	0.010	0.106	0.656
Vertisol	0.009	0.106	0.656
Lowest	0.009	0.105	0.656
Highest	0.012	0.106	0.657
% Difference	27%	1.2%	0.2%

erosion over time. The sensitivity to the occlusion rate is relatively low, indicating that it does not require further calibration.

The sensitivity of P_{loss} to the leaching retention factor R is higher in the Copenhagen region than in Piedmont. P loss with leaching comprises a greater proportion of the total P loss in Copenhagen due to the lower soil erosion, giving R a greater impact. However, a 50 % change in R only changes P_{loss} by 5 % in the sensitivity test in the Copenhagen region, indicating a generally low sensitivity. Thus, it is not a priority to further calibrate R for improvement of the model or to develop the modelling of P leaching, since the impact on the life cycle inventory factors is low.

4. Discussion

4.1. Structure of P pools

Comparing the new version of the model with its previous version, a significant difference is the new structure of the P pools and updates in the interactions between them. Although the model structure is more developed than in the previous version, it is still a major simplification of reality. One of the main simplifications is the exclusion of interactions between inorganic and organic P. This could have implications on the estimation of leaching, for example, as the risk of leaching could depend on the amount of organic P in the soil (McDowell et al., 2020), which in turn can also be influenced by changes in soil organic matter (Jindo et al., 2023), neither of which were considered in the model. However, other models have successfully modelled interactions between soil inorganic P pools without giving consideration to interactions with organic P (Ringeval et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022). Moreover, in several long-term field experiments with application of organic fertilisers, soil

Table 7

The effect of the partitioning coefficient (f) for applied RPF-P on the inventory factors (P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, P harvest factor $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and mineral P fertiliser substitution factor $F_{P_{FS}}$) for $f = 0, 0.5$ and 1 .

Years	5	25	100	500	
$F_{P_{Loss}}$	$f = 0$	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03
	$f = 0.5$	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02
	$f = 1$	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
$F_{P_{Harvest}}$	$f = 0$	0.00	0.02	0.06	0.10
	$f = 0.5$	0.07	0.09	0.10	0.13
	$f = 1$	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.13
$F_{P_{FS}}$	$f = 0$	0.01	0.14	0.47	0.85
	$f = 0.5$	0.33	0.49	0.66	0.85
	$f = 1$	0.66	0.87	0.87	0.87

Table 8

The 100 year-inventory factors (P loss factor $F_{P_{Loss}}$, harvested P factor $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ and mineral P fertiliser substitution factor $F_{P_{PFS}}$) obtained from modelling with the default constants of the model and when each of these constants is changed to a 50 % lower or 50 % higher value. The constants are the residual P release (μ_{res}) of biologically precipitated biosolids (Bio-P) and sewage-sludge ash (SS ash), occlusion rate (γ) and retention (R). The sensitivity of R was tested both in Copenhagen (DK) and in Piedmont (IT). The percentage change of the inventory factor when a parameter is changed up or down is presented in the right-hand columns.

	50 % lower value	Standard value	50 % higher value	%Change with lower value	%Change with higher value
$F_{P_{Loss}}$					
μ_{res} Bio-P	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.2 %	-4.2 %
μ_{res} SS ash	0.01	0.01	0.01	13.0 %	-10.5 %
γ	0.01	0.01	0.01	-1.7 %	1.7 %
R , DK	0.01	0.01	0.01	-4.7 %	4.7 %
R , IT	0.06	0.06	0.07	-1.1 %	1.1 %
$F_{P_{Harvest}}$					
μ_{res} Bio-P	0.13	0.13	0.13	-1.8 %	1.2 %
μ_{res} SS ash	0.08	0.09	0.10	-16.6 %	11.4 %
γ	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.0 %	0.0 %
R , DK	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.0 %	0.0 %
R , IT	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.1 %	-0.1 %
$F_{P_{PFS}}$					
μ_{res} Bio-P	0.80	0.82	0.84	-2.3 %	1.6 %
μ_{res} SS ash	0.47	0.59	0.68	-21.4 %	14.7 %
γ	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.0 %	0.0 %
R , DK	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.1 %	-0.1 %
R , IT	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.0 %	0.0 %

organic P concentration and form remained largely unaffected. Keller et al. (2012) found no effect on the concentration and forms of organic P after 30 years of inputs of animal manure. Similarly, Geisseler et al. (2011) found no significant difference in soil organic P concentrations after 29 years of inputs of manure and mineral fertiliser. In the Askov field experiment in Denmark, organic P added with animal manure was also found to mineralise rapidly (Rubaek and Sibbesen, 1995). Annaheim et al. (2015) studied the effect of dairy manure, compost and sewage sludge application for 62 years, and found that the composition of organic P was similar in all treatments. Based on these studies, it seems that organic P in organic fertilisers is mineralised quickly in the topsoil after application, indicating that the amount of soil organic P is not greatly affected by the type of organic fertiliser added. This supports the interactions between organic and inorganic P not being very important for the model output, justifying the exclusion of these interactions in the model.

4.2. P fertiliser substitution

The case study shows that, as expected, the strategy for mineral fertiliser application has a large impact on the mineral P fertiliser substitution factor ($F_{P_{PFS}}$) (Fig. 2e and f). The large impact of the fertilisation strategy, especially on the substitution factor, indicates the importance of defining this precisely to correspond with the real practice of farmers in the region of interest. It also supports the importance of the update of the model including the possibility for the model user to define the fertilisation strategy manually.

Regulations vary substantially between countries, and it is common that application of organic fertiliser P, such as animal manure, is limited by the N content rather than the P content. Therefore, the substitution factor of an RPF can be much lower if it is applied on an animal farm than on an arable farm, as demonstrated by ten Hoeve et al. (2018).

The substitution factor $F_{P_{PFS}}$ for struvite on a 100-year period was estimated to be 87 % both in the Copenhagen region and in Piedmont, while for SS ash the substitution was 59 % in Copenhagen and 42 % in Piedmont. Using the previous version of the model, the $F_{P_{PFS}}$ of mineral fertiliser (which has a partitioning coefficient similar to struvite) was estimated to be 31 % for application in Denmark (ten Hoeve et al., 2018). Most LCA studies assume a higher substitution than that calculated by ten Hoeve et al. (2018).

It is worth noting that the substitution factors used in many LCA studies are based on mineral fertiliser equivalents, i.e. how much fertiliser is needed to produce the same amount of plant P uptake as the RPF

in a short-term field crop trial. In contrast, this model simulates how much less fertiliser a farmer in the area will use in response to the application, given that the regulations and recommended practices in the area are followed. It is believed that this is a much more solid foundation for defining a substitution factor, since it better reflects the true consequences of an RPF application.

The difference in the substitution factors between the previous and new versions of the model may be due to the partitioning factor of mineral fertiliser, which in this study was set to 1, while in the previous version it was 0.8. This means that the initial plant P availability of mineral P was assumed to be 100 %. If there is excessive labile P, the equilibrium between the pools P_L and P_{sec} causes sorption of P to P_{sec} until the sorption capacity is reached.

4.3. P loss

Soil erosion is the dominating P loss pathway, and leaching is only a small fraction of this, which is in agreement with the literature (Alewell et al., 2020). Due to the great variation in soil erosion between regions (Panagos et al., 2015), the soil erosion rate was found to be one of the most important parameters for $F_{P_{Loss}}$, which is in agreement with this study's hypothesis. It is noteworthy that the PLCI model considers P loss from the defined system, which is the agricultural field. Modelling of the subsequent fate of P after leaving the system boundary should be included in the impact assessment of an LCA. Borrelli et al. (2018) estimated the ratio between sediment yield and gross erosion to 15.3 %, and Panagos et al. (2022a) predicted that 82 % of displaced P would re-deposit within or close to agricultural fields and on average 18 % would reach the riverine system. If a user of the PLCI 2.0 model is interested in calculating the transport to riverine systems, multiplication by the P delivery ratios calculated by Panagos et al. (2022a) could be adopted.

The total P displaced by erosion from agricultural land was estimated by Panagos et al. (2022a) to be 2 kg P ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ on average in the EU and 9 kg P ha⁻¹ on average in Italy. The total P loss estimated in the present study (including erosion and leaching) for Copenhagen and Piedmont, respectively, was 2.5 and 15 kg ha⁻¹. One reason for the higher estimate for Piedmont compared with Panagos et al. (2022a) could be the higher soil total P considered. Scherer and Pfister (2015) estimated the P emissions from common crops using the USLE equation model and the SALCA model and compared their results with the emission factors reported in the ecoinvent life cycle inventory database (also based on the SALCA model). According to Scherer and Pfister (2015), values on P

losses in ecoinvent underestimate the true emissions of P by up to one order of magnitude. For example, they estimated the emissions from wheat cultivation to be $5.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg P kg crop⁻¹. Using the average wheat yield of Denmark, [ten Hoeve et al. \(2018\)](#) calculated that the estimate by [Scherer and Pfister \(2015\)](#) corresponds to an emission of 4 kg P ha⁻¹ for wheat in Denmark. In conclusion, the P loss estimated in the present study is within the range of estimates given in other studies.

Apart from the soil erosion rate, another parameter that can also affect $F_{P_{Loss}}$ significantly is soil type, as demonstrated in the sensitivity analysis ([Table 6](#)). Thus, it is important to select the right soil type, especially in regions where soil erosion is high. Additionally, another important parameter is the partitioning coefficient f of the RPF. The smaller the partitioning to the labile pool, the more will be lost with soil erosion before becoming plant-available. This means that the model is capable of showing significant differences between fertilisers with varying temporal P availability.

4.4. P harvest

In the first 40 years of the simulations, RPFs with higher partitioning to P_L resulted in higher $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ in both regions ([Fig. 2](#)). However, over a longer time period, $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ increases for RPFs with a greater residual pool in Piedmont. The stricter fertilisation strategy results in higher uptake efficiency of the residual RPF-P, which can be seen to have a greater impact on $F_{P_{Harvest}}$ than soil erosion.

$F_{P_{Harvest}}$, as well as $F_{P_{Loss}}$, are also relatively sensitive to α_{max} . The update of the PLCI model to include country-specific α_{max} for all EU countries, as well as the calculation tool that calculates α_{max} by selecting a crop distribution, is a significant improvement to the model. The calculation of α_{max} accounts for the varying P content between crops, but the P content of residues was set to 0.11 % for all crops, similar to the assumption made by [Panagos et al. \(2022b\)](#). In reality, the P content in residues also varies between crops. However, the P levels in harvested residues are generally much lower than in the grain, meaning that the impact on the inventory factors is limited. The crop P uptake in perennial trees was calculated assuming that the partitioning of P to the fruit and foliage is similar for all perennial trees. Differences in the partitioning between tree species were not included due to the lack of available data. Therefore, α_{max} of crop distributions high in perennial trees has a greater uncertainty and these factors should be used more carefully. For a country with a crop distribution high in trees, such as olives, vineyards and fruit trees, the model user is encouraged to use the calculation tool if the aim is to model a crop distribution with annual crops and use specific data for the trees of interest if data are available. Generally, crop distributions vary significantly between regions within many countries. Therefore, users of the model are encouraged to use the calculation tool to define the crop distribution that they wish to model.

4.5. Model application

When using the model, it is important to be aware that it estimates average inventory factors for a region. This is also of particular interest to LCA modellers because they will often have limited knowledge about the specific fields on which an RPF will be applied. If the LCA modeller has more information, for example that the RPF will primarily be applied on a specific crop type or soil type, this can be defined in the model and provide more precise results for their case. However, it is important to note that the model is not designed to calculate precise P losses from a specific field.

Future work should aim to validate the model by comparing it with field studies. The present study is large-scale and covers the whole area of the EU. This makes validation at such a scale challenging. Nevertheless, trust in the model is built by confirming that it produces sensible outputs in relation to input parameters and by conducting a thorough sensitivity analysis. Such methods are widely used in other large-scale water quality models to build trust in their results (e.g., [Li et al.,](#)

[2022](#); [Strokal et al., 2021](#)). It should be stressed that parts of the model in the present study were partially validated, including the calculation of $P_{erosion}$ and the calculation of P_{CaCl2} from P_L , which both showed fair correlations between calculated and measured data (Eq (11) $r = 0.65$ and Eq (10) $r = 0.58$). The model estimated low $P_{leaching}$ in relation to $P_{erosion}$, which is generally true in most places. However, the calculation of $P_{leaching}$ could be improved by considering parameters that increase the risk of greater leaching in some regions, such as preferential flow ([Djordjic et al., 2004](#)), and interactions between organic and inorganic P. Furthermore, future work could improve the calculation of $P_{harvest}$ by making this parameter depend on the varying crop yield between regions. There is also potential to improve the slow-release factor μ_{res} , which was inherited from the previous version of the model and brings uncertainty, especially for the modelling of RPFs with low immediate availability (low f). Future studies should aim to calibrate this factor for different fertiliser types.

5. Conclusions

As demonstrated in the case study, the PLCI 2.0 model can now be used to demonstrate the differences between P fertiliser application in different regions of the EU and calculate region-specific life cycle inventory factors for RPFs, showing significant differences between fertilisers with varying P availability. Based on the case study, it is concluded that both the region in which an RPF is applied and the type of RPF have a significant impact on the inventory factors. It was not clear that either the region or the type of RPF had a greater impact on the results, which invalidates the hypothesis that the region has a greater impact. However, as also hypothesised, the difference in soil erosion rates and P fertilisation practices between the regions of Copenhagen and Piedmont had a strong impact on the P loss factor and P fertiliser substitution factor respectively. The results point to the importance of defining the fertilisation regime to fit with farmers' real practice in the region of interest, which is now possible with the new, more dynamic version of the model.

Based on the sensitivity analysis, it is concluded that the inventory factors show sensible relationships with input parameters. The P loss factor increases with a higher soil erosion rate, higher groundwater recharge, lower partitioning of RPF-P to the labile pool and higher sorption capacity of the soil S_{max} , as higher sorption of labile P to secondary minerals leads to less P being taken up by plants and the loss of a larger fraction with soil erosion. The P harvest factor increases especially with higher maximum crop P uptake α_{max} and decreases with higher Olsen-P as the use efficiency of the added P increases when the soil P status is low. The P fertiliser substitution factor increases with greater partitioning of P to the labile pool and decreases with soil erosion.

In conclusion, the new PLCI 2.0 model provides a dynamic tool for LCA practitioners to estimate inventory factors for RPFs. The model is relatively easy to use and at the same time captures differences between fertilisers and regions in the EU.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maja Rydgård: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Lars Stoumann Jensen:**

Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Carolien Kroeze:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Maryna Strokal:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Kurt Möller:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Sander Bruun:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Lars Stoumann Jensen reports financial support was provided by European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://doi.org/10.17894/ucph.c376d9f4-514a-4ce1-92ff-1f059b3c748> and in the supplementary materials.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141088>.

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